

2-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (HMBATSC) as a spectrophotometric reagent for simultaneous second order derivative determination of nickel(II) and vanadium(V)

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Abstract : 2-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (HMBATSC) has been synthesized, characterized and utilized as a reagent for simultaneous second order derivative spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II) and vanadium(V) without separation. The reagent (HMBATSC) reacts with nickel(II) and vanadium(V) at pH ~6.0, forming soluble yellow and green coloured species respectively. Nickel and vanadium present in the mixture are simultaneously determined without solving the simultaneous equations by measuring the second derivative amplitudes at 409.5 and 432 nm respectively. Further, the derivative amplitudes obey Beer's law at 409.5 and 432 nm for Ni^{II} and V^V in the range 0.058–2.186 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and 0.051–4.074 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. A large number of foreign ions do not interfere in the present method. The present simultaneous method is applied for the determination of nickel(II) and vanadium(V) in alloy steel samples.

Keywords : Simultaneous determination, nickel(II), vanadium(V), derivative spectrophotometry.

Derivative spectrophotometry is a useful means of resolving two overlapping spectra and eliminating matrix interferences in the assay of multicomponent systems. This include zero-order technique¹ and solving of simultaneous equations². In addition, the component being determined should make a reasonable contribution to the total derivative reading of the mixture at the selected wavelengths. A good number of derivative spectrophotometric methods were proposed for the simultaneous determination of metal ion in mixtures in recent times³. Wang *et al.*⁴ proposed a second derivative spectrophotometric method for the determination of nickel and vanadium in petroleum and petroleum residues. In the present paper, we are reporting a highly sensitive and selective second order derivative spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous determination of nickel and vanadium in complex materials without solving simultaneous equations.

Experimental

Absorbance and pH measurements were made on a Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer (Model UV-160A) fitted with 1 cm quartz cells and Phillips digital

pH meter (Model L1 613) respectively. Second-order derivative spectra were recorded with a scan speed of fast (nearly 2400 nm min⁻¹); slit width of 1 nm with nine degrees of freedom, in the required wavelength range (nm). The derivative amplitudes measured at required wavelengths were plotted against concentration of nickel(II) or vanadium(V) to obtain the calibration plots.

Reagents :

Preparation of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone :

The reagent (HMBATSC) was prepared by the published procedure⁵. 11.25 g of 2-Hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde (1) and 4.55 g of thiosemicarbazide (2) were dissolved in sufficient volume of methanol and the mixture was refluxed for 60 min. The contents were allowed to cool and the product was separated by filtration. A crude sample (yield 80%) was obtained (C₉H₁₁O₂SN₃). The resultant product was recrystallised twice from hot methanol. Pure light yellowish green crystals of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (HMBATSC) (3) (m.p. 220–222 °C) were obtained.

A 0.01 M solution of HMBATSC in dimethyl formamide (DMF) was employed in the present studies.

Applications :

The present method was applied for the determination of Ni^{II} and V^V in alloy steel samples. The results obtained are presented in Table 2, which are in good agreement with the certified values.

The present method is simple, sensitive and highly selective for the simultaneous determination of Ni^{II} and V^V in admixtures without separation and without solving simultaneous equations.

References

1. A. M. Wahbi, H. Abdine and S. Balaiah, *J. Assoc. off. Anal. Chem.*, 1977, **60**, 1175; A. F. Fell, *Proc. Anal. Div. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **15**, 260; M. Bedair, M. A. Korany and F. A. El-Yazbi, *Sci. Pharm.*, 1986, **54**, 31.
2. M. A. Korany, A. M. Wahbi, M. A. Elsayed and S. Mandour, *Anal. Lett.*, 1984, **17**, 1373.
3. A. I. Jimenez, F. Jimenez and J. J. Arias, *Analyst (London)*, 1989, **114**, 93; J. Ghasemi and A. Niazi, *Microchemical Journal*, 2001, **68**, 1; K. Sozgen and E. Tutem, *Talanta*, 2004, **62**, 971; L. L. Kolomiets, L. A. Pilipenko, I. M. Zhmud and I. P. Penfilvo, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 1999, **54**, 28; M. I. Toral, P. Ritche, A. E. Tapia and J. Hernandez, *Talanta*, 1999, **50**, 183; H. Eskandari and G. Saghseloo, *Anal. Sci.*, 2003, **19**, 1513.
4. L. Wang, W. Liu and H. Zhang, *Fenxi Huaxue.*, 1990, **18**, 618.
5. P. T. Sah and S. A. Peoples, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Edn.*, 1954, **43**, 513.
6. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longman, 1962, p. 479; I. M. Kolthoff and R. Bletcher, "Volumetric Analysis", Vol. III, 'Oxidation Reduction Reactions', Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1957, 634.
7. A. I. Buseve and V. M. Invanov, *Zh. Anal. Chim.*, 1963, **18**, 208.